

bred at the Agricultural Research Station, Bombuwela, is a 120-day samba rice variety recommended for cultivation

in the low-country wet zone of Sri Lanka. It is resistant to blast, has tolerance for iron toxicity and is

moderately resistant to gall midge and storage pests. It has good grain quality. ■

Performance of IET7041 in nitrogen variety trial

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A field trial was conducted on a black clayey soil with high organic matter content, medium phosphorus and high potassium contents, and a pH of 7.5 during kharif (Jun-Nov) 1979 at the Regional Center, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Maruteru, A. P. Six prerelease lines and two released varieties (Table 1) constituted the main plots, and four nitrogen levels were the subplots in a split-plot design with three replications. A basal applica-

Table 1. Details of entries in nitrogen variety trial, APAU, 1979 kharif.

IET no.	Designation	Cross	Maturity (days)	100-grain wt (g)	Rice type ^a
5656	RP975-109-2	Sona/RPW6-13	155	26	LB
5854	RP1017-76-1-4-3	Sona/Mahsuri	150	18	MS
6056	RP894-61-1-3-7-2	CR44-35/W12708	155	19	MS
6212	RP1064-14-2-2	RP31-49-2/Patnai 23	155	25	SB
6314	RP1045-23-2-1	RP31-49-2/LMN	160	25	SB
7041	MTU7029	Vasista/Mahsuri	155	19	MS
	Pankaj (check)		155	28	LB
	Mahsuri (check)		150	16	MS

^aLB = long, bold; SB = short, bold; MS = medium, slender.

tion of 30 kg P₂O₅ and 30 kg K₂O/ha was applied. Nitrogen was applied 50% at transplanting, 25% at 25 days after transplanting (DT), and 25% at 50 DT.

IET7041 (MTU7029), developed at APAU, yielded highest (Table 2). The optimum level of nitrogen for it was 30

kg/ha. It had the highest panicle number at all nitrogen levels.

IET7041 should be suited for good yields on soils with high organic matter at lower nitrogen inputs in kharif on the Krishna and Godavari deltas of A.P. ■

Table 2. Summary of results of nitrogen variety trial, APAU, 1979 kharif.

Nitrogen level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	IET7041	IET5656	Pankaj	IET6314	IET6056	IET6212	IET5854	Mahsuri (check)
0	5.9	5.1	5.0	4.6	5.0	4.1	4.5	3.8
30	6.0	5.2	4.9	4.8	4.3	4.1	4.1	3.2
60	6.3	5.2	5.0	4.8	4.1	4.4	3.7	3.2
90	6.4	4.8	4.6	4.3	4.5	4.3	3.0	2.4

C.D. (P = 0.05) for varieties, 0.6 t/ha; for nitrogen levels, 0.3 t/ha.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Studies on false-smut disease caused by *Ustilaginoidea virens* on paddy in Karnataka, India

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False smut on paddy has occurred in Karnataka for more than 3 decades. The preliminary survey conducted for more than 5 years indicates that the disease occurs on both modern and local improved varieties throughout the state

during the kharif, particularly on varieties that are late sown and flower late (usually from November). The data collected indicate that the disease incidence on some varieties varies from less than 1% to more than 50%. The percentage of incidence has been taken on the panicle basis, irrespective of the number of smut balls formed on each panicle.

Some varieties showed less than 10% incidence: IET2885 (7.92), IET2886 (5.62), IET1789 (1.08), IR26 (0.48), IET2295 (4.33), Sona (0.77), and IET3359 (1.42). Varieties among the IRON entries of kharif 1976 that showed

more than 50% disease incidence were IR4427-315-2-3, IR4442-45-2-1, IR4722-36-1, IR5853-31, and IR2863-31-3. Among the NSN entries of kharif 1976 with more than 50% disease incidence were RP894-61-1-10-7, RP974-4-7-6-2, RP6-590-22-5-4-1, Biplat, and IR2071-588-1-1-1.

Further information indicates that the number of smut balls varies from 1 to 6/panicle; 2-4 smut balls have been observed on more than 50% of infected panicles; 1-6 smut balls have been observed on 16%, 32%, 26%, 14%, 8.20%, and 3.80% of infected panicles.